

**Prediction of binaural speech intelligibility in noise and reverberation for
normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners**

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1 A binaural model is proposed to predict speech intelligibility for normal-hearing (NH)
2 and hearing-impaired listeners in rooms. It combines two existing models. The
3 *leclere2015* model takes binaural room impulse responses (BRIRs) as inputs and
4 accounts for the temporal smearing of the speech by reverberation, but only works
5 with stationary noises for NH listeners. The *vicente2020* model takes the speech and
6 noise signals at the ears as well as the listener audiogram as inputs and accounts
7 for modulations in the noise and hearing loss, but cannot predict for the temporal
8 smearing of the speech by reverberation. The new model takes the audiogram, BRIRs
9 and ear signals as inputs to account for the temporal smearing of the speech, the
10 masker modulations and hearing loss. Its predictions corresponded well to the speech
11 reception thresholds measured in seven experiments. The proposed model can do
12 predictions than neither of the two original models can make when the target speech
13 is influenced by reverberation and the noise has modulations and/or the listeners
14 have hearing loss. In terms of model parameters, four methods were compared to
15 separate the early and late reverberation, and two methods were compared to account
16 for hearing loss.

17 **Keywords:** Speech intelligibility, auditory modelling, Binaural hearing, Rever-
18 beration, Hearing loss

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19 INTRODUCTION

20 Hearing-impaired (HI) listeners often complain about difficulties to understand speech in
21 noisy and reverberant rooms. The aim of the present study was to develop a model able to
22 predict their ability to understand speech in such environments.

23 One key mechanism to understand speech in noisy environments is spatial release from
24 masking (SRM), the ability to benefit from a difference in position between the target
25 speech and noise masker sources ([Bronkhorst and Plomp, 1988](#)). It can be separated in two
26 mechanisms, better-ear listening and binaural unmasking. Better-ear listening originates
27 from differences of interaural level differences (ILDs) between the target and masker signals
28 at the two ears, which results in differences of signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the two ears,
29 allowing us to benefit from the better SNR between the two ears to better understand the
30 target speech. Binaural unmasking relies on the differences of interaural time differences
31 (ITD) produced by the target and masker. It can be modeled by assuming that the listener
32 is able to equalize the masker at the two ears, and partially cancel it to improve intelligibility
33 ([Durlach, 1963](#)). SRM is usually reduced for HI listeners ([Glyde et al., 2011](#)). First, their
34 elevated hearing thresholds decrease the audibility of the speech signal, which can limit the
35 benefit of better-ear listening (since the speech signal at the better ear may not be audible).
36 Second, they have a reduced sensitivity to the temporal fine structure of sounds ([Füllgrabe
37 and Moore, 2017](#)), which might slightly limit their ability for binaural unmasking ([Vicente
38 et al., 2021](#)).

39 Room reverberation has several detrimental effects on speech intelligibility in noise.
40 It temporally smears the target speech, which degrades its intelligibility ([Houtgast and](#)
41 [Steeneken, 1985](#)). Reverberation also temporally smears the masker. This can be detrimen-
42 tal to intelligibility when the masker is modulated in amplitude, as it reduces the intelligibil-
43 ity benefit coming from listening in the “dips” of the masker, also called dip listening benefit
44 ([Festen and Plomp, 1990](#); [Miller and Licklider, 1950](#)). SRM is also reduced by reverberation
45 ([Plomp, 1976](#)). Sound reflections travelling around the head reduce ILDs, impairing better-
46 ear listening. These reflections also decorrelate the sound at the two ears, reducing binaural
47 unmasking ([Lavandier and Culling, 2008](#)). The sensitivity of HI listeners to reverberation
48 has been a matter of debate. They seem to be as much affected as normal-hearing (NH)
49 listeners by the effects of reverberation on the speech and the masker in monaural conditions
50 ([Cueille et al., 2022](#)). There is some evidence that this is also the case in binaural conditions
51 ([Helfer and Wilber, 1990](#); [Xia et al., 2018](#)).

52 Several binaural speech intelligibility models have been proposed in the literature (for a
53 review, see [Lavandier and Best, 2020](#)). Most predict SRM and the effects of reverberation on
54 SRM. Some of these models can also predict the degradation of speech intelligibility caused
55 by reverberation temporally smearing the target speech but only for NH listeners ([Leclère](#)
56 [et al., 2015](#); [van Wijngaarden and Drullman, 2008](#)). Others models allow predictions for HI
57 listeners ([Beutelmann and Brand, 2006](#); [Beutelmann et al., 2010](#); [Vicente et al., 2020](#)), but
58 cannot account for the temporal smearing of the target speech by reverberation. [Rennies](#)
59 [et al. \(2011\)](#) developed three extensions of the model proposed by [Beutelmann et al. \(2010\)](#).
60 Those extensions allow to predict speech intelligibility with HI listeners and temporally

61 smeared speech. [Rennies et al. \(2019\)](#) also proposed a fourth extension which allows to
62 predict speech intelligibility in conditions where the later reflections of the target speech can
63 be useful to intelligibility. However, to the best of our knowledge, these model versions were
64 only tested for NH listeners and a stationary noise masker. [Andersen et al. \(2016, 2018\)](#)
65 proposed binaural models based on the models of [Taal et al. \(2011\)](#) and [Beutelmann et al.](#)
66 [\(2010\)](#). The models of [Andersen et al. \(2016, 2018\)](#) can predict the performances of NH
67 listeners in reverberant conditions, and the effect of non-linear speech processing similar to
68 those used in hearing aids. However, nothing is currently implemented so that they could
69 predict the effect of hearing loss. During the Clarity Prediction Challenge ([Barker et al.,](#)
70 [2022](#)), several binaural models using a machine learning approach were tested on datasets
71 involving HI listeners and signals processed by different speech enhancement algorithms. In
72 principle, these models are able to do predictions for HI listeners wearing hearing aids in
73 rooms. However, the more accurate models require being trained with speech and conditions
74 very similar to the evaluation material beforehand.

75 A new model was developed here, combining the models of [Vicente et al. \(2020\)](#) and
76 [Leclère et al. \(2015\)](#). It is able to predict the speech reception thresholds (SRTs, the SNRs
77 for 50% intelligibility) for datasets involving at the same time non-stationary noises, NH and
78 HI listeners in binaural and reverberant conditions, something that the two original models
79 cannot do. Using seven datasets described in more details below, this model is shown to
80 account for SRM and the influence of reverberation on SRM, dip listening and the influence
81 of reverberation on dip listening, temporal smearing of the target speech by reverberation,
82 and hearing loss.

83 DESCRIPTION OF THE MODELS

84 Original models

85 Both the [Vicente et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Leclère et al. \(2015\)](#) models (*vicente2020* and
86 *leclere2015* in the following and in [Lavandier et al. \(2022\)](#)) are based on a model de-
87 veloped by [Lavandier and Culling \(2010\)](#). This model allows to predict better-ear listening
88 and binaural unmasking advantages by frequency bands, taking the signals recorded at the
89 ears of the listener as inputs. Instead of the target speech, the target signal consists of
90 a speech-shaped noise with the long-term characteristics of the target speech (magnitude
91 spectrum and ITD). This is done in order to avoid that the short pauses between words lead
92 to very low SNRs. Better-ear listening is implemented by evaluating the SNR at each ear by
93 frequency band. The maximum SNR across ears is integrated across frequency using a SII
94 weighting ([ANSI S3.5, 1997](#)) to obtain a broadband target-to-interferer ratio. The binaural
95 unmasking advantage is computed in each frequency band following a formula proposed by
96 [Culling et al. \(2005\)](#), and integrated across bands using the SII weightings. The binaural
97 unmasking advantage and better-ear ratio are summed in order to obtain a binaural ratio.
98 The binaural ratio is a value in dB which reflects speech intelligibility. A higher binaural
99 ratio represents a better speech intelligibility. Differences in binaural ratios can be compared
100 to differences in SRTs. To be compared to absolute SRTs, a reference need to be chosen,
101 which is often the average SRT measured in the experiment ([Lavandier et al., 2022](#)).

102 The *leclere2015* model is an extension of the [Lavandier and Culling \(2010\)](#) model based on
103 the concept of useful-to-detrimental ratio ([Lochner and Burger, 1964](#)). It takes the binaural

104 room impulse responses (BRIRs) at the ears of the listener as input. The target BRIR is
105 separated into an early and a late part. The early part is considered as useful for speech
106 intelligibility, while the late part is considered as detrimental and is concatenated with the
107 masker BRIR. The early-late separation can be done using several temporal window shapes:
108 rectangular, linear, sigmoid (Leclère *et al.*, 2015). The *leclere2015* model uses “linear”
109 windows: the early window starts with a constant amplitude of 1, followed by a linear
110 decrease to 0, while the late window starts at 0 and then increases linearly to 1, so that the
111 two windows sum to 1 at each instant. These linear windows are defined by two parameters.
112 The early-late limit (ELL) defines the duration of the constant portion in the windows. The
113 decay duration defines the duration of the linear decrease/increase. Even if Leclère *et al.*
114 (2015) found that the best model performances were obtained when these two parameters
115 were room-dependent, *leclere2015* uses room-independent ELL and decay duration, fixed to
116 30 ms and 25 ms, respectively (Leclère *et al.*, 2015). These values were shown to be the
117 best compromise solution when these parameters are fixed across rooms/positions. This
118 model accounts for the detrimental effects of reverberation on the target speech and SRM
119 for stationary noises. However, because it does not take the masker signal and the listener’s
120 audiogram as inputs, it cannot predict the effects of the masker modulations and hearing
121 impairment.

122 The *vicente2020* model is a different extension of the Lavandier and Culling (2010) model
123 with two main improvements: a short-term analysis to take into account the effect of masker
124 modulations (Collin and Lavandier, 2013), and an internal noise modelling the effect of
125 hearing impairment (Vicente *et al.*, 2020). Its structure is shown on the right part of Figure

1. It takes the target and masker signals at the ears of the listener as inputs. The target signal is a speech-shaped noise with the long-term characteristics of the target speech. The masker signal is segmented in time frames and the better-ear ratio and binaural unmasking advantage are calculated by frequency bands in each time frame (Collin and Lavandier, 2013). An internal noise spectrum is also implemented at each ear, with spectrum levels depending on the listener audiogram and the external sound broadband level. Vicente et al. (2020) approximated this external sound level with the masker level, assuming that the broadband SNR is below 0 dB. The masker and target signals need to be calibrated to the external sound level. When calculating the better-ear SNR, the SNR at each ear is computed using the higher level between the internal noise and the external masker. The binaural unmasking advantage is computed as done by Lavandier and Culling (2010), except that it is set to zero as soon as the target or masker level is below the internal noise level at one ear. The *vicente2020* model allows to predict SRM for NH and HI listeners. However, because it does not consider the early and late parts of the target separately (and thus considers them both useful), it cannot account for the temporal smearing of the target by reverberation.

Proposed model

Model structure

The model proposed here is a combination of *vicente2020* and *leclere2015*. Its structure is presented on Figure 1. It consists in applying *vicente2020* on inputs prepared following

146 the *leclere2015* approach, as also done in one of the models of [Rennies et al. \(2011\)](#). Instead
147 of using the target and masker signals at the ear, the original speech and noise materials
148 and the BRIRs at the ears are taken as inputs. This allows to re-create the stimuli used in
149 the experiments, except that the early and late targets can be separated. This cannot be
150 done with only the stimuli at the ears. The target BRIR is separated in an early and a late
151 part as in *leclere2015*. The speech material is averaged across sentences and the average
152 target signal is convolved with the early and the late target BRIR. The early target signal
153 is taken as input in *vicente2020*, as the useful signal. The late target signal is summed with
154 the masker signal, that is to say the noise material convolved with the masker BRIR. The
155 resulting signal is taken as input *vicente2020*, as the detrimental signal.

156 In order to predict the effect of hearing loss, two different methods were tested here to
157 calculate the internal noise level. The first method was the one used in *vicente2020*, where
158 the internal noise depends on the listener audiogram and the external sound broadband level.
159 In the second method, this broadband level is replaced by the external sound spectrum, so
160 that the internal noise level in a given frequency band depends on the external sound level
161 in that particular band rather than on its broadband level. This modification influences the
162 predictions only for HI listeners (i.e. here for the datasets from [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#) and
163 [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#)).

164 The processing of the signals and BRIRs is detailed in Figure 2. After convolution with
165 the BRIRs, the target and masker signals need to be calibrated to the presentation level,
166 corresponding to the sound level at which the stimuli were played during the experiment.
167 This level was approximated as the masker level here, due to the masker signal usually

FIG. 1: Structure of the proposed model. The first block represents the signal processing (detailed in Figure 2). The second block represents the *vicente2020* model

FIG. 2: Processing of the signals and BRIRs in the proposed model

168 having a fixed level higher than the target level in the experiments considered. In the
 169 proposed model, the calibration of the early and late target signals necessitates that they
 170 are multiplied by the gain required to calibrate the level of the “full” target (the average of
 171 the speech sentences convolved with the “full” target BRIR) to the presentation level.

172 ***Choice of the early-late limit***

173 [Leclère et al. \(2015\)](#) tested several shapes for the temporal windows used to do the early-
174 late separation and showed that they led to very similar results. Here only linear windows (as
175 used in the room-independent model *leclere2015*) were considered. Both the ELL and the
176 decay duration can be varied to improve the model performances, so that for a given decay
177 duration an ELL can be found to reach optimal performance ([Leclère et al., 2015](#)). Here, it
178 was decided to only vary the ELL and keep the decay duration at a fixed value of 25 ms (the
179 default value used in *leclere2015*), except when the computation method required another
180 decay duration value (see the Kokabi method below). Four methods of ELL computation
181 were tested.

182 First, a room-independent ELL fixed at 30 ms (as in *leclere2015*) was tested. The corre-
183 sponding model version was called “model-RI” (Room-Independent).

184 The second approach was based on the mixing time. The ELL was set to the physical
185 mixing time defined as the moment when the diffuse reverberation tail begins ([Lindau et al.,](#)
186 [2012](#)). It was estimated using the method proposed by [Abel and Huang \(2006\)](#), based on the
187 calculation of the echo density profile of each BRIR, meaning that the ELL is room/position-
188 dependent. To calculate the echo density, a rectangular time window of 23 ms slides along
189 the target BRIR. Within each time window, the standard deviation of the sound pressure is
190 calculated. The proportion of samples outside the interval “mean window value \pm window
191 standard deviation” is calculated. The echo density is defined in each time window as
192 the ratio between this proportion and the proportion of samples which would be outside

193 the window standard deviation if the samples followed a Gaussian distribution. At the
194 beginning of the BRIR, the sound pressure equals zero, so the echo density is also zero. As
195 time increases the sound becomes diffuse and the sound pressure of the BRIR within the
196 time window starts to resemble a Gaussian distribution, so that the echo density tends to
197 one. The physical mixing time ELL is defined as the instant when the echo density reaches
198 unity. The version of the model using this ELL was called “model-Abel”.

199 The third model version varied the ELL depending on the BRIR interaural cross-
200 correlation (IACC) based on a linear regression proposed by [Kokabi et al. \(2018\)](#), in a
201 first attempt to develop a room-dependent version of *leclere2015*. They used *leclere2015*
202 on BRIRs simulated by [Rennies et al. \(2011\)](#) (1 room, 4 distances, 2 source positions), as
203 well as BRIRs from a simulated room with varying absorption coefficients (4 absorption
204 coefficients). To predict the SRTs of [Rennies et al. \(2011\)](#) and those measured in their
205 own study, *leclere2015* was tested with several ELLs, and a linear regression was done in
206 order to find a correlation between the ELLs leading to the best predicted SRTs and the
207 IACCs. The regression $ELL = 143 - 202 \times IACC$ gave the best results, with a correlation
208 coefficient of 0.74. This ELL computation was tested here. It was developed with a 1-ms
209 decay duration, and the same decay duration value was thus used here. This version of the
210 model was called “model-Kokabi”.

211 The fourth method to compute the ELL was based on the BRIR short-term IACC. The
212 similarity of the reflections at the two ears is used to decide whether they are detrimental,
213 assuming that reverberation makes the late target more masking when it is more different
214 at the ears thus limiting binaural unmasking ([Lavandier and Culling, 2008](#); [Leclère et al.](#),

215 [2015; Rennie *et al.*, 2019](#)). It is based on the work of [Rennie *et al.* \(2019\)](#), who showed
216 that reflections might be defined as useful or detrimental depending on whether they are
217 useful/detrimental for SRM and binaural intelligibility, rather than whether they are early
218 or late. Here the IACC was measured in rectangular temporal windows of 23 ms. The ELL
219 was defined as the instant when the short-term IACC first becomes inferior to 0.6. This value
220 was arbitrarily chosen to test the concept, but the estimated ELLs were very similar when
221 it was chosen between 0.7 and 0.5. This version of the model was called “model-IACC”.

222 **Model evaluation**

223 The eight versions of the proposed model, corresponding to the four computations of EEL
224 and the two computations of internal noise, were evaluated using the data from seven exper-
225 iments. The first experiment of [Lavandier *et al.* \(2012\)](#) was used to consider the influence
226 of reverberation on SRM (for stationary noise and NH listeners). The third experiment of
227 [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#) was selected to involve the influence of reverberation on SRM
228 and the temporal smearing of the target (for stationary noise and NH listeners). The first
229 experiment of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) was chosen to involve the effect of reverberation
230 on dip listening (for frontal sources generating limited binaural effects, and NH listeners).
231 The third experiment of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) allowed to consider the dip listening
232 benefit and the temporal smearing of the target by reverberation (for frontal sources gen-
233 erating limited binaural effects, and NH listeners). The fourth experiment of [Collin and
234 Lavandier \(2013\)](#) was used to combine the effects of dip listening and SRM, even if only
235 at a low reverberation level (for NH listeners). The experiment of [Cueille *et al.* \(2022\)](#) was

236 chosen to involve the effects of reverberation on the temporal smearing of the target for NH
237 and HI listeners (in monaural conditions). The dataset 1 of [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#) allowed
238 to test the influence of reverberation on SRM for stationary and modulated noises, with
239 NH and HI listeners. Among these datasets, the third experiment of [Collin and Lavandier](#)
240 [\(2013\)](#) and the experiment of [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#) cannot be predicted by *leclere2015* and
241 *vicente2020*, as they involve the effect of the temporal smearing of the target speech (that
242 *vicente2020* cannot predict) and the effect of the noise modulations of the masker (that
243 *leclere2015* cannot predict). The experiment from [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#) also involves the
244 effect of hearing loss, which cannot be predicted by *leclere2015*.

245 Testing the proposed model requires access to the collected data and the signals used dur-
246 ing the experiments, but also to the BRIRs and the original raw speech and noise materials
247 used to create this stimuli. Thus, as a first step, the models were tested here using our own
248 datasets. However, overall, the models were tested on data measured in four different labs,
249 with four different speech material, in two languages, using four different procedures. The
250 experiments from [Lavandier et al. \(2012\)](#) and [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#) were adaptive
251 SRT measurements done at Cardiff University (UK) with unpredictable English sentences
252 from the Harvard Sentence List ([IEEE, 1969](#)). The experiments from [Collin and Lavandier](#)
253 [\(2013\)](#) were adaptive SRT measurements done at ENTPE (France), with unpredictable
254 French sentences from an open set developed by [Raake and Katz \(2006\)](#). The experiment
255 from [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#) was done at CRNL (France) and measured full psychometric func-
256 tions, with French sentences from a closed set matrix-type speech material ([Jansen et al.,](#)
257 [2012](#)). The dataset from [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#) involves adaptative SRT measurements done at

258 Macquarie University (Australia), with English sentences from an open set speech material
259 ([Bench et al., 1979](#)).

260 The predicted SRTs were compared with the measured data, and with the predictions
261 of the original models *leclere2015* and *vicente2020*. The figures comparing the predictions
262 of the proposed model to those of the original models are shown in the paper only for
263 the two datasets which neither *leclere2015* or *vicente2020* can predict, that is the third
264 experiment of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) and the experiment of [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#). For
265 the other datasets the corresponding figures can be found in the supplementary materials
266 (see supplementary materials at [URL will be inserted by AIP]).

267 The four ELL calculation methods were tested for all datasets, except the one from
268 [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#). The Kokabi and IACC versions could not be tested with this dataset
269 because the stimuli are monaural. The two methods of internal noise calculation were only
270 compared with the two datasets involving HI listeners, as the internal noise does not affect
271 the predictions for NH listeners. For each dataset and for all model versions, the Pearson's
272 correlation coefficient between the average measured and predicted SRTs was calculated,
273 along with the mean and largest absolute errors between average data and predictions.
274 Furthermore, the individual predictions of the HI listeners are shown in the supplementary
275 materials for the two datasets involving HI listeners, along with the Pearson correlation
276 coefficient between the individual measured and predicted SRTs and the mean and largest
277 absolute errors between individual data and prediction across conditions. The individual
278 predictions of the NH listeners are not shown, as the models give very similar predictions
279 for the NH listeners, because they do not use individual inputs other than the audiograms.

280 Thus they cannot predict the individual variability of the NH listeners ([Lavandier et al.,](#)
281 [2021](#)).

282 **Implementation of the predictions**

283 Depending on the dataset the target signal was created by averaging between 60 and 280
284 sentence waveforms. The datasets involving only NH listeners did not give information on
285 the presentation level used during data collection. The presentation level was fixed at 65
286 dB SPL for these datasets. This did not affect the predictions as the presentation level only
287 affects the model through the internal noise that has an effect only for the predictions of
288 HI listeners (unless very soft levels are considered, which was never the case here). When
289 the audiograms of the NH listeners were unavailable, their hearing thresholds were fixed at
290 0 dB HL at all frequencies.

291 To compare absolute SRTs and binaural ratios (the model output), a reference needs to
292 be chosen (it does not influence the relative differences in predictions across conditions).
293 The average measured SRT within each dataset was chosen as reference ([Lavandier et al.,](#)
294 [2022](#)). Before comparison to the measured data, the binaural ratios were inverted (higher
295 ratios reflect better intelligibility and lower SRTs). Inverted binaural ratios were offset by
296 subtracting their mean and adding the corresponding average SRT across conditions and
297 listeners (the reference), thus aligning the inverted binaural ratios with the measured SRTs.
298 The models *leclere2015* and *vicente2020*, implemented and made available by [Lavandier](#)
299 [et al. \(2022\)](#), were used here using the same assumptions (whenever relevant).

300 **DATASETS USED TO TEST THE MODELS AND RESULTS OF THE PREDIC-**
301 **TIONS**

302 The datasets involved only NH listeners, unless otherwise specified. The proposed model
303 versions based on the external broadband level and spectrum level give identical predictions
304 for NH listeners, so that four new model versions are compared. For the datasets with HI
305 listeners, the corresponding difference in internal noise implementation leads to eight tested
306 new model versions. The performance statistics for the different model versions are shown
307 in Table I. The estimated ELL obtained with the four ELL separation methods can be found
308 in Table II.

309 **Lavandier et al. (2012)**

310 In the experiment 1 of [Lavandier et al. \(2012\)](#), the stimuli were convolved with BRIRs
311 measured in a real room and spectral envelope impulse responses (SEIRs). The SEIRs
312 were obtained by removing the temporal characteristics of the BRIRs, in order to remove
313 the ITDs while preserving the ILDs, so that better-ear listening is possible while binaural
314 unmasking is not. A single stationary noise was tested at two distances (0.65 m, “near”,
315 and 5 m, “far”) and three orientations (-25°, “left”, 0°, “front”, +25°, “right”). The target
316 speech was always at the same position (near right). The measured SRTs and predictions of
317 the four versions of the proposed model can be found in Figure 3. The SRM is highlighted
318 by comparing the SRTs in the left and front conditions to those in the co-located condition

319 (near right). An interaction between reverberation and SRM was also observed, as there
320 was less SRM in the far conditions.

321 As expected, *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* accurately predict this dataset (Suppl. Fig. 1)
322 and give performance statistics similar to the proposed model.

323 The four versions of the proposed model give similarly accurate predictions. The Kokabi
324 and IACC versions slightly overestimate the SRTs in the BRIRs conditions and underesti-
325 mate them in the SEIRs conditions. The performance statistics in Table I do not reflect
326 these differences (which remain lower than 1 dB) and show similar accuracy for the four
327 versions. It is interesting to note that even though their predictions are similar, the four
328 model versions estimate different ELLs for this dataset. As can be seen in the Table II, the
329 Abel version considered the whole target BRIR as useful (as the echo density never reached
330 1), while the Kokabi and IACC versions estimated an ELL lower than the room-independent
331 ELL at 30 ms.

332 **Lavandier and Culling (2008)**

333 In the experiment 3 of [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#), a single stationary noise was always
334 spatially separated from the target speech, the noise being 65° to the left of the listener
335 and the target being 65° to its right. The room absorption coefficients used for the target
336 and noise were controlled separately for each source, testing four coefficients: 1, 0.7, 0.5,
337 0.2. The measured SRTs and model predictions are shown in Figure 4. The SRT increase
338 observed as the target absorption coefficient decreases (reverberation increases) highlights

FIG. 3: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Lavandier et al. (2012). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

339 the temporal smearing of the target speech. The SRT increases as the masker absorption
 340 coefficient decreases, highlighting the detrimental effect of reverberation on SRM.

341 The *leclere2015* model has similar performance statistics as the proposed model (Table
 342 I). On the other hand, *vicente2020* is inaccurate (Suppl. Fig. 2). This is expected, as
 343 *vicente2020* does not consider the early and late targets separately and cannot predict the
 344 effect of the temporal smearing of the target speech.

345 The room-independent and Abel model versions give results similar to those of *leclere2015*
 346 (Suppl. Fig. 2). They overestimate the SRT when the target absorption coefficient is 1 and
 347 slightly underestimate it when it is 0.5. The Kokabi version gives similar predictions, but is
 348 even less accurate when the target absorption coefficient is 0.5. The IACC version gives the

FIG. 4: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Lavandier and Culling (2008). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

349 less accurate predictions. It underestimates the SRT when the target absorption coefficient
 350 is 1 and 0.7, and largely overestimates it when it is 0.2. The performance statistics also show
 351 this difference in performance, with the Kokabi and IACC versions leading to larger mean
 352 and largest prediction errors. For this dataset, the Abel version considered the whole target
 353 BRIR as useful for the two highest target absorption coefficients, and estimated ELLs close
 354 to 30 ms for the two lowest coefficients (Table II). The Kokabi version followed an inverse
 355 trend, estimating low ELLs (below 15 ms) for the highest absorption coefficient and relatively
 356 larger ELLs (49 ms and 26 ms) for the two lowest absorption coefficients. The IACC version
 357 estimated low ELLs (below 15 ms) for all conditions.

358 **Collin and Lavandier (2013) - Experiment 1**

359 In the experiment 1 of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#), SRTs were measured with stationary
360 noise or noise modulated by the envelope of a speech signal comprised of one, two or four
361 voices. The interferer was tested at three distances (65, 125, and 500 cm) in front of the lis-
362 tener in a lecture hall. Increasing its distance increased the relative amount of reverberation
363 for the interferer. The target was always at 65 cm in front of the listener. The measured
364 SRTs and model predictions can be found in [Figure 5](#). A dip listening benefit is observed, as
365 the SRTs are lower when the masker is modulated. This dip listening benefit is reduced by
366 reverberation when the interferer distance increases. Note that room coloration also made
367 the noises less masking when their distance increased, counterbalancing the reduction of
368 dip listening for the modulated noises (for more discussion on this effect, see [Collin and](#)
369 [Lavandier \(2013\)](#)).

370 The *vicente2020* model predicts this dataset as accurately as the proposed model, while
371 *leclere2015* gives inaccurate predictions ([Suppl. Fig. 3](#)) with a correlation between data
372 and prediction of 0.42. This was expected as *leclere2015* cannot predict the effect of masker
373 modulations.

374 The four versions of the proposed model give accurate predictions for this dataset ([Table](#)
375 [I](#)). The room-independent, Abel and IACC versions slightly underestimate the SRT in the
376 conditions with one-voice and two-voice modulated maskers, and slightly overestimate it in
377 the conditions with a stationary masker. In other words, the dip listening benefit appears
378 slightly overestimated. The Kokabi version is a bit more accurate in this regard. For this

FIG. 5: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Collin and Lavandier (2013) in their first experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

379 dataset, the Abel version estimated an ELL of 23 ms, against 0 ms for the Kokabi version
 380 (that is to say, the early target BRIR consisted only of the decaying part of 1 ms), and 11
 381 ms for the IACC version (Table II).

382 Collin and Lavandier (2013) - Experiment 3

383 In the experiment 3 of Collin and Lavandier (2013), a stationary noise and a one-voice
 384 modulated noise were tested, always close to the listener (at 65 cm). The target was tested
 385 at two distances: 65 cm and 10 m. The target and the interferer were always in front of
 386 the listener in a L-shaped room. The measured SRTs and model predictions are shown in
 387 Figure 6. The temporal smearing of the target speech is highlighted by the SRT increase

388 between the 65-cm and 10-m conditions. The dip listening benefit is highlighted by the SRT
389 difference between the stationary and one-voice modulated masker. There was no significant
390 interaction between the target distance and interferer modulations.

391 Contrary to the new model, *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* give inaccurate predictions for
392 this dataset, as can be seen in Figure 7. The *vicente2020* model leads to a correlation
393 between data and prediction of only 0.58 and large prediction errors (Table I), because it
394 cannot account for the effect of the temporal smearing of the target speech. The *leclere2015*
395 model provides a correlation of 0.97, but also large prediction errors, because it cannot
396 account for the effect of masker modulations and dip listening.

397 The Abel model version gives the best predictions, but appears to slightly overestimate
398 the SRTs at the shortest distance (65 cm) and underestimate them at the larger distance
399 (10 m), underestimating the effect of the temporal smearing of the target speech. This
400 tendency was found at a larger degree with the room-independent and Kokabi versions, the
401 Kokabi version being the worst. The performance statistics show that these two versions
402 lead to larger prediction errors (see Table I). The IACC version follows an inverse trend,
403 overestimating the temporal smearing of the target speech. For this dataset, the Abel version
404 estimated ELLs of 25 ms and 14 ms for the 65 cm and 10 m conditions, respectively. The
405 Kokabi version estimated ELLs of 22 ms and 104 ms. The IACC version estimated ELLs of
406 11 ms and 0 ms.

FIG. 6: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Collin and Lavandier (2013) in their third experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

407 **Collin and Lavandier (2013) - Experiment 4**

408 In the experiment 4 of Collin and Lavandier (2013), a stationary noise, a one-voice mod-
 409 ulated noise and a two-voice modulated noise were tested. The target was always in front of
 410 the listener. The stationary and two-voice modulated noises were tested in three configura-
 411 tions: in front (co-located with the target), asymmetrical (+25°) and symmetrical (+25° and
 412 -25°). The one-voice modulated noise was only tested in the co-located and asymmetrical
 413 configurations. All sources were tested at the same fixed distance (65 cm) in a meeting room
 414 (the room also used in the experiment 1 of Lavandier et al. (2012)). The measured SRTs
 415 and model predictions can be found in Figure 8. A dip listening benefit is observed, as the

FIG. 7: Same as Fig. 6 but with the predictions of *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* (as well as model-RI for comparison). The predictions of *leclere2015* are identical with stationary and modulated noise, as the noise modulations are not taken as input.

416 SRTs are lower with modulated noises. SRM was also observed, as the SRTs were lower in
 417 the asymmetrical configuration compared to the co-located condition. The SRM was much
 418 reduced in the symmetrical configuration.

419 The *vicente2020* model accurately predicts this dataset (Table I), with performance statis-
 420 tics similar to those of the proposed model. The *leclere2015* model is able to predict the
 421 effect of spatial configuration, but not the effect of masker modulations (Suppl. Fig. 4). Its
 422 performance statistics are slightly worse than those of the other models.

423 The room-independent, Abel and IACC versions show accurate predictions. They slightly
 424 overestimate the SRTs for the stationary noise, implying that the dip listening benefit is
 425 slightly overestimated. The SRTs are also underestimated for the two-voice-modulated noise
 426 in the symmetrical configuration (+/-25°). The Kokabi version might provide slightly more

FIG. 8: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) in their fourth experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

427 accurate predictions, as also reflected by the performance statistics (Table I). The ELLs
 428 estimated for this dataset were 32 ms, 0 ms and 11 ms, for the Abel, Kokabi and IACC
 429 versions, respectively.

430 **Cueille et al. (2022)**

431 [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#) tested both NH and HI listeners. The HI listeners had a mean four-
 432 frequency pure tone average (PTA4) of 45.2 ± 11.3 dB HL. All the stimuli were monaural.
 433 A stationary noise and an unintelligible two-voice vocoded speech (as a proxy for modulated
 434 noise) were tested. Reverberation was applied either only on the target speech (four rever-
 435 beration times tested), only on the interfering noise (one reverberation time), or on both

436 target and noise (one reverberation time). An anechoic condition was also tested. The stim-
437 uli for the HI listeners were amplified using a linear frequency-dependent gain set with the
438 NAL-RP prescription rule (Dillon, 2012). The comparison between the two original models
439 and the room-independent version of the proposed model using the external sound spectrum
440 as input is presented in Figure 9. The measured SRTs and the predictions from the four ELL
441 versions of the proposed model with the external spectrum as input are shown in Figure 10,
442 while those using the external broadband level appear in Figure 11. The scatterplots of the
443 individual predictions are provided in the supplementary material (Suppl. Fig. 6).

444 The effect of hearing loss can be seen with the lower SRTs of the NH listeners. The
445 effect of the temporal smearing of the speech is highlighted by the SRT increases when the
446 reverberation time used for the target speech increases. Very limited dip listening benefit
447 (difference between black and grey SRTs) was observed in the data, only for the NH listeners
448 in the less reverberant conditions. Cueille *et al.* (2022) found a larger dip listening benefit
449 at lower SNRs, considering the full psychometric functions of the listeners.

450 Figure 9 shows that *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* inaccurately describe this dataset, while
451 the room-independent version of the proposed model gives accurate predictions. The *vi-*
452 *cente2020* model leads to a correlation of 0.59 and large mean and largest prediction errors,
453 because it does not account for the temporal smearing of the target speech. The *leclere2015*
454 model provides a correlation of 0.73 and large prediction errors, because it cannot predict
455 the effect of hearing loss and the large differences between the SRTs of the NH and HI
456 listeners.

457 The Kokabi and IACC model versions could not be tested here because the stimuli are
458 monaural. The room-independent model version with an internal noise based on the external
459 sound spectrum can predict all the trends of the dataset, even if it overestimates the dip
460 listening benefit by 1 dB (Fig; 10). The Abel version gives similar predictions, and slightly
461 underestimates the SRT variations between the conditions with low and high reverberation
462 times, thus leading to slightly lower correlation between data and predictions and a larger
463 maximum prediction error. For this dataset, the Abel version estimated large ELLs (between
464 39 ms and 75 ms; Table II). The larger ELLs were obtained for the intermediate reverberation
465 times (0.5 s and 0.8 s), while the smaller ELLs were obtained for the highest reverberation
466 times (1.1 and 1.5 s).

467 Figure 11 shows that the model versions that use the external sound broadband level
468 were less accurate than the versions using the external sound spectrum. When focusing on
469 the room-independent versions, taking the broadband level as input led to an overestimation
470 of the SRT difference between the NH and HI listeners by 3 dB (Fig. 11), while the version
471 using the external spectrum underestimated this difference by 1 dB (Fig. 10). This is also
472 apparent in the individual predictions (Suppl. Fig. 6), where the SRTs of some listeners
473 were largely overestimated in all conditions when using the external broadband level , but
474 not when using the external spectrum (correlation of 0.73, mean error of 3.9 dB, largest
475 error of 16.2 dB with the broadband level; correlation of 0.75, mean error of 2.8 dB and
476 largest error of 9.6 dB with the spectrum).

FIG. 9: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Cueille et al. (2022). Predicted SRTs are displayed for *vicente2020* and *leclere2015*, as well as model-RI (using the external sound spectrum) for comparison. The predictions of *leclere2015* are identical with stationary and modulated noise.

477 **Vicente et al. (2021)**

478 [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#) tested both NH and HI listeners. The HI listeners had a PTA4 of 30.6
 479 ± 5.8 dB HL. In the dataset 1 of their experiment, they used stationary speech-shaped noise
 480 and noise-vocoded speech as maskers. Three levels of reverberation were used for the masker,
 481 with room absorption coefficients of 1, 0.7 and 0.2. The target sentences were anechoic. The
 482 masker remained at 6.16 m of the listener, with an azimuth of 16.4°. The target sentences
 483 were simulated at 2 m of the listeners, with three tested azimuths: -90°, 20° and 40°. The
 484 stimuli of the HI listeners were amplified with the NAL-RP prescription rule. The measured

FIG. 10: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with the internal noise depending on the external sound spectrum, for two ELL calculation methods (the two binaural methods could not be tested with monaural stimuli).

485 SRTs and predictions from the four ELL versions of the model with the external spectrum as
 486 input are shown in Figure 12, while Figure 13 compares the two room-independent version.
 487 The predictions of the original models are presented in the supplemental materials (Suppl.
 488 Fig. 5), along with the scatterplots of the individual predictions of the proposed model
 489 (Suppl. Fig. 7). The effect of hearing loss is highlighted with the higher SRTs of the HI
 490 listeners. The dip listening benefit is highlighted with lower SRTs for the noise-vocoded
 491 speech than for the speech-shaped noise. The SRM is highlighted with lower SRTs for the
 492 target azimuths -90° and 40° . Increasing reverberation reduced both SRM and dip listening.
 493 The predictions of the original models are presented in the supplemental materials (Suppl.

FIG. 11: Same as Figure 10 but for the model versions with the internal noise depending on the external sound broadband level

494 fig. 5), along with the scatterplots of the individual predictions of the proposed model
 495 (Suppl. Fig. 7).

496 The *vicente2020* model accurately predicts this dataset, with predictions very similar to
 497 the versions of the proposed model using the external sound broadband level (Suppl. Fig.
 498 5). This was expected, as the two models are equivalent when the target speech is not
 499 temporally smeared by reverberation. The *leclere2015* model gives poor performances, as it
 500 does not take into account the effects of hearing loss and noise modulations.

501 The four ELL separation methods give very similar predictions both for the model versions
 502 based on the external sound spectrum (Fig. 12) and those based on the external broadband
 503 level (not shown). The Kokabi method has slightly worse performances than the other three
 504 methods, slightly underestimating the SRTs at low reverberation levels. All model versions

505 seem to overestimate the dip listening benefit by about 2 dB in the condition where the
506 room absorption coefficient is equal to 1. For this dataset, the Abel version considered the
507 whole target BRIR as useful, while the Kokabi and IACC versions estimated ELLs of 0 ms
508 and 5 ms, respectively.

509 Figure 13 shows that the two internal noise implementations give very similar predictions,
510 the version based on the external spectrum being slightly less accurate. Using the external
511 spectrum led to an underestimation of the SRT difference between the NH and HI listeners
512 by 1 dB, while using the broadband level gave accurate predictions. The two versions gave
513 similar performance statistics for the individual predictions of the HI listeners (Suppl. Fig.
514 7; correlation of 0.71, mean error of 1.5 dB, largest error of 5.3 dB with the broadband level;
515 correlation of 0.70, mean error of 1.5 dB and largest error of 5.8 dB with the spectrum).

517 **DISCUSSION**

518 **Comparison with the original models**

519 The *vicente2020* model was inaccurate for the datasets where the speech was temporally
520 smeared, that is to say, [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#), the third experiment of [Collin and](#)
521 [Lavandier \(2013\)](#), and [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#). The *leclere2015* model gave inaccurate results
522 for the datasets with modulated noise or HI listeners, that is to say, the first and third
523 experiment of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#), and [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#), respectively. These
524 results were expected, as *vicente2020* does not discriminate between early and late target
525 reflections, and *leclere2015* does not take the masker modulation characteristics as input

FIG. 12: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by [Vicente et al.](#)

(2021) using a stationary noise (SSN) or vocoded-speech (VS) masker. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with the internal noise depending on the external sound spectrum, for four ELL calculation methods. These methods give very similar predictions, so that the corresponding lines mostly overlap.

526 nor the hearing profile of the listener. In contrast, the room-independent version of the pro-
 527 posed model gave predictions as accurate as *vicente2020* for the datasets with a modulated
 528 interferer or HI listeners, and as accurate as *leclere2015* for the datasets with a temporally
 529 smeared target speech. It was also able to describe the data from [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#)
 530 and the experiment 3 of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#), something that neither *vicente2020*
 531 nor *leclere2015* can do. The proposed model thus combines the advantages of each origi-
 532 nal model, so that it extends their performance and generalizability to a larger range of
 533 conditions.

FIG. 13: Same as Figure 12 but for the predictions of the RI-model versions based on the external spectrum and broadband level

534 **Comparison of the model versions**

535 The two model variations discussed here are the target BRIR separation method and the
 536 internal noise calculation. The former affects the prediction of the effect of the temporal
 537 smearing of the target speech, while the later affects the prediction of the effect of hearing
 538 loss.

539 Changes in ELL affected the predictions for BRIRs with strong reverberation, but usually
 540 had little to no effect for BRIRs with little reverberation. This can be seen with the datasets
 541 from Lavandier *et al.* (2012) and Vicente *et al.* (2021) where large changes in ELL between
 542 model versions had almost no effect on the predictions.

543 The room-independent and Abel versions gave similar results for the datasets from La-
 544 vandier and Culling (2008), and the first and fourth experiments of Collin and Lavandier

545 (2013). They differed only for two datasets. For the third experiment of Collin and La-
546 vandier (2013), the Abel version was more accurate, while the room-independent version
547 underestimated the effect of reverberation on the target. For the experiment of Cueille *et al.*
548 (2022), the room-independent version was more accurate, with the Abel version slightly un-
549 derestimating the effect of reverberation on the target. For this dataset the ELL estimated
550 with the Abel version increased for intermediate reverberation times and decreased for high
551 reverberation times, contrarily to the other datasets where the ELL varied monotonously
552 with the reverberation level. In this experiment the room was virtual, created with the
553 ray-tracing software CATT-Acoustic. The generation of the BRIRs is done with a random
554 projection of rays across the room, a stochastic process. This could explain why the ELLs
555 do not vary monotonously, as the detailed pattern of reflections randomly changes between
556 BRIRs.

557 The Kokabi version was less accurate than the other versions with the datasets involving
558 high levels of reverberation, that is to say, Lavandier and Culling (2008) and the third
559 experiment of Collin and Lavandier (2013). This is in accordance with the conclusions of
560 Kokabi *et al.* (2018), who developed their linear regression based on long-term IACC at
561 low and intermediate reverberation levels only. Our results indicate that the efficiency of
562 this regression decreases at high levels of reverberation. It is interesting to note that this
563 model version gave slightly better predictions than the others at very low reverberation
564 levels, that is to say in some conditions of the first and fourth experiments of Collin and
565 Lavandier (2013). This could suggest that the linear regression might be appropriate for low
566 reverberation levels. Alternatively it could indicate that using a shorter decay duration is

567 more relevant then. Note however that low reverberation levels correspond to situations in
568 which temporal smearing of the target will probably have negligible effect on intelligibility
569 (Lavandier and Culling, 2008), greatly limiting the interest for the early-late separation to
570 start with.

571 The model version based on short-term IACC gave similar performances to the room-
572 independent version, except for the dataset from Lavandier and Culling (2008). The IACC
573 version then estimated ELL shorter than the room-independent ELL, leading to a large
574 overestimation of the effect of the temporal smearing of the target speech. Note that the
575 method is binaural and could not be tested on the dataset from Cueille *et al.* (2022) also
576 involving high levels of reverberation. Overall the estimated ELLs were always very short
577 for this method (below 12 ms, Table II). This would imply that only the direct sound
578 is considered useful and most of the early speech reflections (which can increase speech
579 intelligibility) are considered detrimental, which is not appropriate.

580 Overall, the room-independent and Abel versions of the model gave the best predictions
581 and were accurate for all datasets. The Abel version was more accurate than the room-
582 independent version for one dataset with high level of reverberation, but less accurate for
583 another dataset involving a virtual room. Even if Leclère *et al.* (2015) showed that optimizing
584 the ELL as a function of the room/BRIR could improve intelligibility predictions, the room-
585 independent version of the model could be preferred to the Abel version, because it is simpler
586 to implement and has good performance across the wide range of conditions involved in the
587 seven datasets tested here. The Kokabi and IACC versions were not able to describe with
588 enough accuracy all these datasets.

589 The internal noise only affected the predictions for the two datasets involving HI listeners
590 (Cueille *et al.*, 2022; Vicente *et al.*, 2021). The version using the external sound broadband
591 level was slightly more accurate for the dataset from Vicente *et al.* (2021), while the version
592 using the external spectrum was more accurate with the dataset from Cueille *et al.* (2022).
593 The main difference between the two datasets is the degree of hearing loss of the HI listeners,
594 the HI listeners of Cueille *et al.* (2022) having a higher degree of hearing loss. The internal
595 noise taking the broadband level as input could be too high for the HI listeners with a
596 high degree of hearing loss, while the internal noise using the spectrum would be too low
597 for the HI listeners with a low degree of hearing loss. This assumption is supported by
598 the individual predictions of the dataset from Cueille *et al.* (2022) (Suppl. Fig. 6), which
599 show that considering the broadband level largely overestimates the SRTs of some of the HI
600 listeners. It is also in agreement with the results of Vicente *et al.* (2020), who found that
601 taking the broadband level as input allowed the model to give accurate predictions for HI
602 listeners with a low degree of hearing loss. Overall, it appears at this stage that we cannot
603 tell which internal noise calculation method is better. This requires further investigation,
604 considering yet other datasets.

605 **Comparison with other models from the literature**

606 The main advantage of the proposed model is that it allows for predictions in a large
607 variety of conditions, taking into account the effects of binaural hearing, hearing impairment,
608 reverberation, and interferer modulations. There exist other binaural models which take into
609 account the effect of hearing impairment by taking the listener's audiogram as input, such as

610 the one from [Beutelmann *et al.* \(2010\)](#). This model was tested by [Beutelmann *et al.* \(2010\)](#)
611 and [Ewert *et al.* \(2017\)](#) with HI and NH listeners, as well as modulated and stationary
612 noise. However, it cannot take into account the effect of the temporal smearing of the target
613 speech.

614 There also exist other binaural models which allow to predict the effect of the temporal
615 smearing of the target speech caused by reverberation, such as the ones developed by [van](#)
616 [Wijngaarden and Drullman \(2008\)](#), [Andersen *et al.* \(2018\)](#) and [Rennies *et al.* \(2011\)](#). How-
617 ever, the models of [van Wijngaarden and Drullman \(2008\)](#) and [Andersen *et al.* \(2018\)](#) work
618 only for NH listeners. The models proposed by [Rennies *et al.* \(2011\)](#) are extensions of the
619 model of [Beutelmann *et al.* \(2010\)](#) which can predict the temporal smearing of the target
620 speech. One of those extensions does an early-late separation of the BRIR as in the pro-
621 posed model. Like the original [Beutelmann *et al.* \(2010\)](#) model, these extensions should in
622 principle work for HI listeners and modulated noises. However, to the best of our knowledge,
623 they were so far only tested for NH listeners and stationary noise.

624 When tested in different conditions than those considered here, the model from [Beutel-](#)
625 [mann *et al.* \(2010\)](#) led to similar individual prediction performances than the proposed
626 model, with a correlation of 0.78, and a mean error of 3 dB. The more accurate model
627 version from [Rennies *et al.* \(2011\)](#) gave a correlation of 0.74 and a mean error of 1 dB for
628 individual predictions. The model from [Andersen *et al.* \(2018\)](#) gave correlations between
629 0.97 and 0.98 considering averaged data across listeners. It would be interesting to verify
630 that these models work correctly with HI listeners in reverberant conditions. Unfortunately,
631 the performance statistics of these models cannot be directly compared to the ones obtained

632 with the proposed model, as they were obtained with datasets involving other speech mate-
633 rials and different conditions. It could be interesting to test the proposed model along with
634 the models from the literature on the same datasets in order to compare their performances.

635 The models proposed during the Clarity Challenge allow to predict the performances of
636 HI listeners with hearing aids in reverberant conditions (Barker *et al.*, 2022). Some of these
637 models also have the advantage of being non-intrusive, necessitating only the combination of
638 the speech and noise signals at the two ears, while the proposed model requires the separated
639 target and noise signals as well as the target and masker BRIRs as input, limiting its range
640 of application. However, these other models work with a machine learning approach, and
641 necessitate training with speech and listening conditions similar to the evaluation material
642 beforehand. Furthermore, the Clarity Challenge made no clear separation between the
643 training and test materials, which creates the risk that overfitted machine learning models
644 are rewarded.

645 **Limitations of the proposed model**

646 The dataset from Cueille *et al.* (2022) is slightly less accurately predicted than the other
647 datasets tested here, with larger prediction errors. This might be partly explained by the
648 external sound level used in the model. During the experiment, the target speech was set
649 at a fixed sound level of 50 dB SPL for the NH listeners, while the interfering noise (which
650 was louder than the speech in most conditions that led to negative SRTs) varied in level
651 depending on the condition. In the model, the external sound level was fixed to the target
652 speech level for all conditions. Even if the higher noise levels would have been a better

653 approximation of the external sound levels at negative SNRs, these levels cannot be used
654 as a model input because they are fixed by the SRT that corresponds to the model output.
655 The use of the target level could have led to an underestimation of the internal noise of the
656 HI listeners in some conditions and affected the predictions.

657 The experiment from [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#) is also not perfectly predicted, with a
658 correlation coefficient of 0.85 between measured and predicted SRTs. The room-independent
659 version of the model underestimates speech intelligibility in the conditions with an anechoic
660 target, and overestimates it in the conditions with a moderately reverberant target. This
661 is similar to the predictions obtained with *leclere2015*. According to the model predictions,
662 this intelligibility increase (SRT decrease) between the anechoic and moderately reverber-
663 ant conditions would be due to coloration which would have influenced better-ear listening
664 ([Leclère et al., 2015](#)). However, the listeners did not seem to take any advantage of this
665 coloration.

666 The model slightly overestimates the dip listening benefit for the experiment 4 of [Collin](#)
667 [and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) and the datasets of [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#). This
668 is something that was already observed by [Vicente et al. \(2020\)](#). It is likely a misprediction
669 from the better-ear listening component, as the dip listening overestimation is present even
670 in the conditions where there is no binaural unmasking. For example, in the dataset of
671 [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#), with a target azimuth of 20° , a dip listening benefit of 2.7 dB is
672 observed in the data, while the model predicted a benefit of 4.1 dB, of which 4 dB are due
673 to better-ear listening.

674 For the experiment 4 of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) the model overestimates the SRM
675 in the symmetrical condition for the 2-voice modulated maskers. This was already observed
676 with *vicente2020* and could be due to binaural sluggishness not being taken into account
677 for the better-ear listening component of the model ([Vicente and Lavandier, 2020](#)).

678 A drawback of the proposed model is its intrusiveness. As explained above, models
679 such as those of the Clarity Challenge only need the noisy speech signals at the two ears.
680 The proposed model needs the raw, unconvolved target and masker signals, as well as the
681 corresponding BRIRs. This required data explains why the model was yet only tested with
682 datasets available in our laboratories.

683 Note also that the proposed model can only predict differences between conditions in
684 a given dataset. As for *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* ([Lavandier et al., 2022](#)), nothing is
685 implemented to account for the effect of a difference in speech material between two datasets.

686 Finally, the datasets considered here only allow to test a few combinations of individual
687 effects (reverberation, hearing impairment, SRM, dip listening). It could be interesting to
688 further test the model with a dataset involving all these effects simultaneously, but this
689 would require a rather large number of tested conditions.

690 **CONCLUSION**

691 A combination of two binaural speech intelligibility models is proposed. It allows to
692 predict the effects of hearing loss and temporal smearing of the target speech by reverber-
693 ation, along with the effects of SRM and dip listening and the effects of reverberation on
694 these mechanisms. This is done by combining the internal noise function of *vicente2020*

695 and the BRIR separation function of *leclere2015*. The proposed model was as accurate as
696 the two models for the datasets that they could predict. The proposed model was also
697 accurate for the datasets involving at the same time a temporally smearing target and a
698 modulated noise for NH and HI listeners, something that *vicente2020 leclere2015* cannot
699 do. Two of the four tested methods of BRIR separation gave comparable predictions: the
700 room-independent version, for which the ELL is fixed to 30 ms ([Leclère et al., 2015](#)), and
701 the version for which the ELL is defined as the moment when the diffuse reverberation tail
702 begins ([Abel and Huang, 2006](#)). The two other versions based on the IACC (long-term or
703 short-term) were less accurate for at least one of the tested datasets. The room-independent
704 version might be preferable due to its simpler implementation. It gave accurate predictions
705 for seven datasets, with a Pearson’s coefficient correlation between data and prediction rang-
706 ing from 0.85 to 0.98, and a mean absolute prediction error always below 1.4 dB. The two
707 methods of internal noise calculation that were tested gave similarly accurate predictions.
708 The method developed in *vicente2020* was slightly more accurate for HI listeners with a
709 moderate hearing loss, while the new proposed method was more accurate for HI listeners
710 with high hearing loss.

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718 experiments with human participants are taken from previously published studies. The
719 model developed here is being made publicly available within the Auditory Modeling Toolbox
720 (AMT 1.1; [Majdak et al., 2022](#)), along with the code, data and signals used to run the model
721 for an example experiment, as done by [Lavandier et al. \(2022\)](#).

722 **SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS**

723 See supplementary materials at [URL will be inserted by AIP] for the figures comparing
724 the predictions of the proposed model to those of *vicente2020* and *leclere2015*, comparing
725 the predictions of the proposed model with the two types of internal noise implementations,
726 as well as the individual predictions.

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TABLE I: Pearson correlation coefficient, mean and largest errors obtained with the two original models (*vicente2020* and *leclere2015*), as well as the four versions of the proposed model with the internal noise depending on the external sound spectrum. The performances of the models versions taking the external sound broadband level as input are presented in italic, only for the datasets for which this change affects the predictions. The performances in bold highlight the two datasets that the original models do not predict well.

Dataset	vicente2020	leclere2015	model-RI	model-Abel	model-Kokabi	model-IACC
Lavandier et al. (2012)	0.95	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.98
	0.4dB	0.3dB	0.2dB	0.2dB	0.3dB	0.2dB
	0.6dB	0.9dB	0.6dB	0.6dB	0.8dB	0.7dB
Lavandier and Culling (2008)	0.48	0.86	0.85	0.87	0.8	0.85
	1.2dB	0.8dB	0.8dB	0.8dB	1dB	1.8dB
	2.3dB	1.3dB	1.4dB	1.3dB	1.9dB	4.2dB
Collin and Lavandier (2013) Exp.1	0.85	0.49	0.87	0.87	0.89	0.87
	0.5dB	0.6dB	0.4dB	0.4dB	0.3dB	0.4dB
	1.3dB	1.5dB	1.2dB	1.2dB	0.90dB	1.1dB
Collin and Lavandier (2013) Exp.3	0.58	0.97	0.99	0.99	0.86	0.99
	3.6dB	3.1dB	1.1dB	0.3dB	3dB	1dB
	4.5dB	3.4dB	1.4dB	0.7dB	3.6dB	1.4
Collin and Lavandier (2013) Exp.4	0.93	0.87	0.91	0.91	0.93	0.91
	0.6dB	0.7dB	0.6dB	0.6dB	0.4dB	0.5dB
	1.4dB	1.8dB	1.4dB	1.5dB	0.9dB	1.4dB
Cueille et al. (2022)	0.59	0.73	0.93/0.95	0.87/0.89	N/A	N/A
	2.4dB	2dB	0.9dB/1.4dB	1.2dB/1.5dB		
	6.1dB	3.7dB	2.4dB/3dB	3dB/3.6dB		
Vicente et al. (2021)	0.92	0.39	0.87/0.93	0.88/0.93	0.87/0.92	0.87/0.93
	0.9dB	1.7dB	1.1dB/0.9dB	1.1dB/0.9dB	1.1dB/0.9dB	1.1dB/0.9dB
	2dB	4.5dB	2.8dB/1.9dB	2.7dB/1.9dB	2.7dB/2.5dB	2.7dB/1.9dB

TABLE II: Estimated early-late limits (in ms) of the three room-dependent model versions for the seven tested datasets. Each line corresponds to a target BRIR. Datasets are separated by double lines.

Target BRIR	Abel	Kokabi	IACC
LAV12:BRIR	37	6	11
LAV12:SEIR	42(end)	0	11
LAV08:1	243(end)	0	12
LAV08:07	243(end)	12	11
LAV08:05	26	49	0
LAV08:02	21	26	0
COL13:exp1	23	0	11
COL13:exp3-065	25	22	11
COL13:exp3-1000	14	104	0
COL13:exp4	32	0	11
CUE22:0.15	65	N/A	N/A
CUE22:0.5	70	N/A	N/A
CUE22:0.8	75	N/A	N/A
CUE22:1.1	39	N/A	N/A
CUE22:1.5	50	N/A	N/A
VIC21:+20	243(end)	0	5
VIC21:+40	243(end)	0	5
VIC21:-90	243(end)	0	5